

Evaluation of Bt Cotton Scenario in India

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Introduction

Bt cotton is genetically modified by the insertion of one or more genes from a common soil bacterium, *Bacillus thuringiensis*. These genes encode for the production of insecticidal proteins, and thus, genetically transformed plants produce one or more toxins as they grow. The genes those are inserted into cotton produce toxins, named Cry 1Ac, are limited in activity almost exclusively to caterpillar pests (Lepidoptera). However, other strains of *Bacillus thuringiensis* have genes that encode for toxins with insecticidal activity on some beetles (Coleoptera) and flies (Diptera). Some of these genes are being used to control pests in other crops, such as corn. After Bollgard I, Bollgard II was introduced in 2003, representing the next generation of Bt cottons. Bollgard II contains a second gene from the Bt bacteria which encodes the production of Cry 2Ab. WideStrike (a Trademark of Dow AgroSciences) was registered for use in the fall of 2004. Like Bollgard II, WideStrike cotton expresses two Bt toxins (Cry1Ac andCry1F). The use of Bt cotton in India has grown exponentially since its introduction in 2002. (1) Eight years after the deployment of Bt cotton, India became the number one exporter of cotton globally and the second largest cotton producer in the world. India has bred Bt-cotton varieties such as *Bikaneri Nerma* and hybrids such as NHH-44. (2). More than 5 million farmers in India plant nearly 8 Mha of Bt cotton in the country, equivalent to 82 per cent of the total cotton area. The states of Maharashtra, Andhra Pradesh, Gujarat, Punjab, Haryana, Rajasthan, Madhya Pradesh and Karnataka are the major cultivators of Bt cotton. (3)

Controversies

It is feared that due to extensive use of Bt crops, some cotton pests may develop resistance to Bt toxins and this has already been documented for some species. For example, bollworm has developed some resistance to the Cry1Ac, Cry1F, and Cry2A Bt toxins. Negative impacts on non-target arthropods are potential concerns resulting from the use of Bt crops. Concerns were raised

because corn pollen, containing Bt toxins, could be blown onto plants which serve as hosts to monarchs, swallowtails, and other butterflies. This is a minor issue with cotton because, unlike corn, it is not wind pollinated. In India, Bt cotton has been enveloped in controversies due to its supposed failure to reduce the need for pesticides and increase yield. (4) Monsanto's seeds are expensive and lose vigour after one generation, prompting the Indian Council of Agricultural Research to develop a cheaper Bt cotton variety with seeds that could be reused. Qayum and Sakhari (2003) had found that Mahyco-Monsanto Bt cotton was inferior to non-Bt cotton in terms of yields; pesticide use was negligible for both types of cotton; non-Bt farmers had higher profits and lower costs of cultivation, and suspected Bt cotton of a root rot that affected their soils for subsequent crops. They opined Bt cotton had failed on many counts and the claims made by the company were wrong. (5) Chaturvedi et al. (2007) observed that the role of Indian Council of Agricultural Research (ICAR) was minimal in the case of Bt hybrids, unlike in the case of other crop varieties wherein ICAR used to conduct region-wise agronomic trials and advise the farmers on the best ones. This had left the farmers susceptible to any biased claims from the various companies involved, and more exposed to the vagaries of market forces. (6)

Socio-economic Impacts

Bt cotton has several advantages over non-Bt cotton. Increase in yield of cotton due to effective control of three types of bollworms, viz. American, Spotted and Pink bollworms is a major advantage. Insects belonging to Lepidoptera (Bollworms) are sensitive to a crystalline endotoxic protein produced by the Bt gene which in turn protects cotton from bollworms. Use to Bt cotton reduces the insecticide use which in turn helps in potential reduction in the cost of cultivation. As of 2010, cultivation of hybrid species increased to nearly 70% and 90% in 2011. (7) On the yield front, farmers perceived that the Bt cotton technology had a very high positive impact on the yield of main product. Amongst all the environmental factors, pest and disease incidence are greatly influenced by the Bt cotton technology. Under the category of social-economic factors, farmers opine that there was a positive and significant impact of Bt technology on their farm income, standard of living, educational level, employment and equity. Shelton et al. (2002) have suggested that environmental and health risks need to be considered in a comprehensive impact assessment and that Bt crops pose no significant risks to the environment or to human health, and that their positive externalities exceed the potential negative ones. (3) According to Sadashivappa, (2015) Bt technology is very successful in India. He opined that adopting farmers had realized significant benefits through pesticide

reductions, higher effective yields, and higher profits. The agronomic and economic advantages had been sustainable over the first five years of widespread technology use, and there were no signs of declining benefits over time. Even though the diffusion of Bt was a learning process for farmers in the beginning, aggregate adoption had increased steadily and had reached over 80% of India's total cotton area by 2008. Bt technology had helped in achieving a record cotton harvest in India, at a time when other cotton-producing countries were facing a slowdown in production. Sadashivappa also described that there are yield- and profit-enhancing impacts of Bt cotton. According to him the net yield gain of Bt technology was 28%, while the net profit gain was 55%. (8) Even though the diffusion of Bt was a learning process for farmers in the beginning, aggregate adoption has increased steadily and has reached over 80% of India's total cotton area by 2008. (9)

Conclusion

Though Bt cotton provides higher yield than non Bt varieties and its yield is more, non-availability of quality Bt seeds is the most important constraint hindering adoption of Bt cotton production technology. Wherever quality seeds is available, quantity is the limiting factor; in the sense, required quantity of seeds was not available. The other reasons constraining Bt cotton production technology adoption is low adoption by neighborhood farmers, difficulty in adoption of Bt technology, awareness about the technology but non-confirmation of its profitability and non-awareness about the Bt technology. (3)

References

1. KV Kurmanath (22 March 2016). "Bt cotton: how it flowered and is losing lustre now". *The Hindu*.
2. Choudhary, B., & Gaur, K. (2010) Bt cotton in India: A country profile. *ISAAA Series of Biotech Crop Profiles*. ISAAA: Ithaca, NY.
3. Kiresur, V. R., & Ichangi, M. (2011). Socio-economic impact of Bt cotton—A case study of Karnataka. *Agricultural Economics Research Review*, 24(1), 67-81.
4. Shiva, V., & Jafri, A. H. (2004) Failure of GMOs in India (Synthesis/Regeneration 33/Winter). *New Delhi, India: Research Foundation for Science, Technology and Ecology*.
5. Qayum, A. and Sakkhari, K. (2003) Did Bt Cotton Save Farmers in Warangal? A Season Long Impact Study of Bt Cotton – Kharif 2002 in Warangal District of Andhra Pradesh. AP Coalition in Defence of Diversity and the Deccan Development Society, Hyderabad, June 2003.
6. Chaturvedi, S., Wendy, C., Vanga, S.R. and Decio, R. (2007) Environmental risk assessment, socio-economic considerations and decision-making support for LMOs in India, Report Prepared by an inter-disciplinary team from the International Centre for Genetic Engineering and Biotechnology (ICGEB) and Research and Information System

for Developing Countries (RIS) as part of MoEF/GEF-World Bank-aided Capacity Building Project on Biosafety.

7. Tokel, D., Genc, B. N., & Ozyigit, I. I. (2021) Economic impacts of Bt (*Bacillus thuringiensis*) cotton. *Journal of Natural Fibers*, 1-18.
8. Sadashivappa, P. (2015) Socio-economic impacts of Bt cotton adoption in India: Evidence from panel data.
9. Bennett, R. M., Ismael, Y., Morse, S., & Kambhampati, U. S. (2004). Economic impact of genetically modified cotton in India.